

BIFURCATION STUDY AND PARAMETER ANALYSES BOOST CONVERTER

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Abstract : This paper deals with bifurcation analyses in current programmed DC/DC Boost converter and exhibition of chaotic behavior. This phenomenon occurs due to variation of a set of the studied circuit parameters (input voltage and a reference current). Two different types of bifurcation paths have been observed as part as part of another bifurcation arising from variation of suitable chosen parameter.

Keywords : Bifurcation, Chaos, Boost converter Current- programmed control, Initial parameters

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